

Know-How: 7-Eleven, Inc.'S Corporate Strategies Key Factors in Facing Challenges and Creating Solutions

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Abstract:- This research study aims to identify the corporate strategies used by 7-Eleven, Inc. to overcome challenges and achieve success in the retail industry. The study also explores the effectiveness of the company's marketing mix, supply chain management, and customer service initiatives. A total of 50 respondents were randomly selected from customers of 7-Eleven convenience stores in the Science City of Muñoz, Nueva Ecija, Philippines. The results showed that 7-Eleven's guided replenishment system has effectively ensured timely and efficient product delivery. Customers are also satisfied with the store's quality, availability, and variety of products. Most respondents are also satisfied with the customer service of 7-Eleven employees. These findings provide insights for other retailers looking to enhance their corporate/business strategies.

Keywords:- Supply Chain Management, Corporate Strategies, Convenience Store, Innovation.

I. INTRODUCTION

In order to overcome challenges and thrive in the retail industry, businesses must implement effective approaches or corporate strategies in the highly competitive market. One of the key players in this field is the convenience store chain 7-Eleven, which has been growing rapidly across the world.

With more than 83,000 chains of convenience stores across 19 countries, they have become the market leader in the retail industry. Since its introduction into the Philippine market in 1984, 7-Eleven has grown rapidly, with over 3,241 convenience outlets in the country as of June 2022.

Much of 7-Eleven's recent success in the Philippines comes from innovative marketing approaches. Practices like franchising and retail localization help bolster the chain's competitive edge over rival c-stores nationwide. More subtly, these techniques add nuances of Filipino culture to the brand's broadly global image (Matejowsky, 2007).

However, there need to be more studies on corporate strategies in the retail industry to achieve success. Thus, by highlighting and evaluating the effective corporate strategies and practices of 7-Eleven convenience stores, other retailers

can learn to enhance their business operations and stay competitive in the market.

In addition, it seeks to provide insights into the key factors that have contributed to its success and growth, including its supply chain management and customer service initiatives. Hence, this research was conducted.

In this study, the researchers will look at the different strategies used by the 7-Eleven Inc. to attain success. Thus, will give a better understanding on how 7-Eleven has managed to preserve its position as a top retailer by evaluating these strategies and identifying areas where the firm can continue to innovate and develop. Furthermore, this research will give vital insights to other retailers wanting to enhance their strategy and remain ahead of the competition in an increasingly challenging environment.

➤ Statement of the Problem

- What is the profile of 7-Eleven customers?
- What are the major challenges faced by 7-Eleven, Inc. in the convenience retail industry?
- What are the corporate strategies employed by 7-eleven in response to these challenges in terms of:
 - ✓ Marketing Mix (Product, Price, Place, Promotion)
 - ✓ Supply Chain Management
 - ✓ Customer Service Initiatives
- How effective are these strategies in dealing with the challenges faced by 7- eleven?
- How do these challenges affect their in-placed strategies?

II. METHODOLOGY

➤ Sampling Procedure

The researchers used simple random sampling to gather data from the respondents. According to Frod (2023), this procedure is considered to be a gold standard for producing representative samples. Since the respondents are randomly selected it minimized the possibility of biasing the result. Thus, the researcher chose a quantitative method and designed a survey questionnaire as an instrument to gather information, it also includes questions that require the respondents to share their personal insight.

➤ *Respondents*

A sample of 50 respondents were randomly selected who made purchases at 7-eleven convenience stores. A representative from a group of research participants is selected from a larger group, which allows each person to have an equal chance of participating in the study.

➤ *Research Site*

The study was conducted in the Science City of Munoz Nueva Ecija, the 7-eleven convenience stores strategically located near public markets where customers can easily access the store, non-stop incoming of target participants and experiencing the convenience brought by the store.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Customer Profile

The research findings reveal that the majority of the 7-Eleven customers in the sample are Gen Z (11 to 26 years old) and Millennials (27 to 42 years old) having a percentage of 52 and 44 respectively. This suggests that the 7/11 sample customers are predominantly younger. There is a smaller proportion of customers in the higher age groups

(43 to 58 and 59 and above), with a slight majority being female (64%). Given that the sample are majority of Gen Z and Millennials, 68% of the respondents are unmarried.

In terms of purchasing power, majority of the respondents have a family income ranging from 19, 041 - 38, 080 pesos (50%) which is classified as Lower Middle Income class based on the discussion paper series No.2018-20 Profile and Determinants of the Middle Income Class of the Philippines (Albert et. al, 2018). Followed by 28% in the income bracket of 9,521 - 19,040 pesos. There is a smaller proportion of customers in the higher income brackets (38,081 - 66,640 pesos and above 66,640 pesos). This information can help in understanding the income distribution of 7-Eleven customers and potentially guide marketing strategies and product offerings tailored to different income segments. Majority of the respondents' family income are sourced from being employed at government offices (60%).

This research also reveals that 86% of the respondents are visiting 7-Eleven convenience stores at an average of 1 to 2 times a week and 80% of which are spending below 300 pesos on goods and services.

Table 1 Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristic	Frequency (N=50)	Percentage
Age		
11 to 26	26	52%
27 to 42	22	44%
43 to 58	1	2%
59 and above	1	2%
Sex		
Male	18	36%
Female	32	64%
Civil Status		
Single	35	70%
Married	15	30%
Range of Monthly Family Income		
Less than 9, 520 pesos	7	14%
9, 521 - 19, 040 pesos	14	28%
19, 041 - 38, 080 pesos	25	50%
38, 081 - 66,640 pesos	3	6%
Above 66,640 pesos	1	2%

Characteristic	Frequency (N=50)	Percentage
Occupation		
Employed- Private	5	10%
Employed- Government	30	60%
Self-employed	6	12%
Student	9	18%
Frequency of visits to 7-11 stores		
1-2 times a week	43	86%
3-4 times a week	6	12%
5 times and above per week	1	2%
Amount spent when buying at 7-11 stores		
Below 300	40	80%
300-500	8	16%
501-1000	1	2%
More than 1000	1	2%

B. Major Challenges and Key Factors in the Success of 7-Eleven Convenience Stores

In your opinion as a 7-Eleven customer, what are the major challenges/ issues faced by 7-Eleven, Inc. in the convenience retail industry today? (Please select all that apply)

50 responses

Fig 1 Major Challenges/ Issues faced by 7-Eleven Inc. as perceived by Customers

➤ *The major challenges/issues faced by 7-Eleven, Inc. in the convenience retail industry today, as perceived by customers includes:*

- **Increasing competition:** 64% of customers believe that 7-Eleven faces challenges from competitors in the convenience retail industry. This includes competition from other convenience stores, grocery stores, online retail platforms, and other retail formats.
- **Pricing and affordability:** 74% of customers feel that pricing and affordability are major challenges faced by 7-Eleven. This includes concerns about prices of products, overall affordability of items available at 7-Eleven stores.
- **Limited product availability:** 46% of customers feel that 7-Eleven faces challenges related to limited product availability. This includes concerns about out-of-stock items, limited variety, or inadequate supply of certain products at 7-Eleven stores.
- **Changing consumer preferences:** 32% of customers feel that changing consumer preferences pose challenges for 7-Eleven. This includes shifts in consumer preferences

towards healthier options, more sustainable products, or changing demands for convenience and technology.

- **Evolving market dynamics:** 32% of customers believe that 7-Eleven faces challenges due to evolving market dynamics. This includes changes in market trends, regulations, economic conditions, or demographic shifts that impact the convenience retail industry.
- **Cleanliness and hygiene concerns:** 24% of customers feel that cleanliness and hygiene concerns pose challenges for 7-Eleven. This includes concerns related to store cleanliness, food safety, and overall hygiene practices at 7-Eleven stores.
- **Customer service quality:** 18% of customers feel that customer service quality is a challenge for 7-Eleven. This could include concerns related to staff responsiveness, friendliness, and overall service quality at 7-Eleven stores.
- **Limited seating areas:** 2% of customers feel that limited seating areas pose challenges for 7-Eleven. This could include concerns related to the availability of seating areas for customers who wish to consume food or beverages inside the store.

Which of the following key factors do you think are most important for 7/11's success? (Select all that apply)

50 responses

Fig 2 Key factors that are most important for the success of 7-Eleven Inc. as perceived by Customers

➤ *The key factors that are most important for 7/11's success, as indicated by the percentages, are:*

- **Location:** 72% of customers believe that the location of 7-Eleven stores is a crucial factor for its success. This could include convenient and easily accessible locations that are convenient for customers to visit.
- **Convenience:** 82% of customers feel that convenience is a critical factor for 7-Eleven's success. This could include factors such as 24/7 operating hours, a wide range of products available, and easy and quick transactions.
- **Product quality:** 40% of customers believe that product quality is an important factor for 7-Eleven's success.

This could include the freshness, taste, and overall quality of the products sold at 7-Eleven stores.

- **Price:** 40% of customers feel that pricing is a key factor for 7-Eleven's success. This could include competitive pricing, promotions, discounts, and overall affordability of products offered at 7-Eleven stores.
- **Brand reputation:** 36% of customers believe that brand reputation is an important factor for 7-Eleven's success. This could include customers' perception of the brand's image, trustworthiness, and reliability.
- **Customer service:** 30% of customers feel that customer service is a factor for 7-Eleven's success. This could include factors such as friendly and helpful staff, efficient service, and overall positive experiences with the customer service at 7-Eleven stores.

What do you think are the corporate strategies 7-Eleven, Inc. employed to address these challenges in the recent years? (Please select all that apply)

50 responses

Fig 3 Corporate strategies employed by 7-Eleven Inc. to address challenges in the recent years as perceived by Customers

➤ Based on the respondent’s opinions, 7-Eleven, Inc. has employed the following corporate strategies to address the challenges in recent years:

- 58% of the respondents indicated that 7-Eleven has been implementing pricing and promotional strategies. This could involve offering discounts, promotions, or loyalty programs to attract customers and drive sales.
- 52% of the respondents indicated that 7-Eleven has been focusing on expanding its product offerings. This could involve introducing new products, brands, or services to attract more customers and increase sales.
- 58% of the respondents indicated that 7-Eleven has been implementing pricing and promotional strategies. This could involve offering discounts, promotions, or loyalty programs to attract customers and drive sales.

- 40% of the respondents indicated that 7-Eleven has been emphasizing innovation and adaptation to market trends. This could involve introducing new concepts, technologies, or services to meet changing customer demands and stay relevant in the market.
- 58% of the respondents indicated that 7-Eleven has been integrating technologies in their offerings. This could involve incorporating ATMs, charging stations, bills payment services, or other technological innovations to provide added convenience to customers and enhance the overall customer experience.

C. Effectiveness of strategies employed by 7-Eleven in dealing with challenges

➤ Marketing Mix (Product, Price, Place, Promotion)

Table 2 Effectiveness of strategies employed by 7-Eleven Inc. in terms of Product in their Marketing Mix in dealing with challenges as perceived by customers

	1 (Very Dissatisfied)	2 (Dissatisfied)	3 (Neutral)	4 (Satisfied)	5 (Very Satisfied)
Perceived quality of products	0%	0%	18%	66%	16%
Product variations available	0%	4%	26%	56%	14%
Perceived quality of products	0%	0%	36%	52%	12%
Effectiveness of leveraging technology to enhance shopping experience	0%	6%	14%	54%	26%
Healthier food options	2%	16%	48%	30%	4%

- *How would you rate the quality of products sold at 7/11 stores?*

Majority of respondents (66%) rated the quality of products sold at 7/11 stores as 4, indicating a relatively high customer satisfaction. 16% of the respondents gave a rating of 5, which is the highest rating, suggesting that some customers have are very satisfied with the quality of products sold at 7-Eleven. 18% of the respondents gave a rating of 3, which suggests that a small portion of customers have a more moderate satisfaction of the product quality. Overall, the majority of respondents seem to be satisfied with product quality at 7/11 stores, with a significant portion rating it as high (4 or 5).

- *Please rate the product variations available at 7/11 convenience stores.*

56% of the respondents rated 4 which reveals that they are satisfied with the product variations at 7/11 stores, followed by 24% which rated 3 indicating their moderate satisfaction and 14% which rated 5, an indication of being very satisfied. 4% of the respondents gave a rating of 2, which suggests that a small portion of customers are dissatisfied with the product variations. Overall, the majority of respondents seem to be satisfied with product variations available at 7/11 stores, with a significant portion rating it as high (4 or 5).

- *How would you rate the perceived quality of products sold at 7/11 convenience stores in comparison to other stores?*

The majority of customers (52%) rated the perceived quality of products at 7/11 convenience stores as "4", indicating that they perceive the quality of products to be

relatively high. Another significant portion of customers (36%) rated the perceived quality as "3", indicating a moderate perception of product quality. Overall, the data suggests that the perceived quality of products sold at 7/11 convenience stores is generally positive, with a majority of customers rating it as above average (3 or higher on a scale of 1 to 5).

- *Please rate how 7/11 convenience stores have effectively leveraged technology to enhance the shopping experience? (e.g. self-checkout using application, loyalty programs, bills payment, ATM, etc.)*

Majority of respondents (52%) rated 7/11 convenience stores' technology usage as highly effective (4 out of 5). Another significant portion (36%) rated it as moderately effective (3 out of 5). This suggests that 7/11 has made considerable efforts in leveraging technology to enhance the shopping experience, although there is still room for improvement according to some respondents.

- *How would you rate the healthier food options at 7/11 convenience stores?*

Based on the sample customers' opinion, the majority of respondents (48%) rated the healthier food options at 7/11 convenience stores as moderately satisfying (3 out of 5). However, there is still room for improvement, as a significant portion of respondents (18%) rated it as low satisfaction (1 or 2 out of 5). This suggests that 7/11 may need to further enhance their healthier food options to better meet the preferences and expectations of their customers.

- *Please Rate the Price of Products Sold at 7/11 Convenience Stores.*

Fig 4 Satisfaction of Customers in the pricing strategies of 7-Eleven Inc.

Majority of respondents (42%) rated the price of products at 7/11 convenience stores as moderately satisfying (3 out of 5). However, there is room for improvement, as a significant portion of respondents (34%) rated it as low satisfaction (1 or 2 out of 5). This suggests that 7/11 may need to consider adjusting their pricing strategy to better meet the price expectations of their customers.

Table 3 Effectiveness of strategies employed by 7-Eleven Inc. in terms of *Place* in their Marketing Mix in dealing with challenges as perceived by customers

	1 (Very Dissatisfied)	2 (Dissatisfied)	3 (Neutral)	4 (Satisfied)	5 (Very Satisfied)
Cleanliness of Store	2%	12%	24%	54%	8%
Location and Operating hours	0%	0%	4%	36%	60%
Store Layout	0%	6%	18%	60%	16%

- How would you rate the cleanliness of 7/11 stores?*
Based on the ratings, the majority of respondents (54%) rated the cleanliness of 7/11 stores as 4 out of 5, indicating that they consider it relatively clean. However, a significant portion of respondents (24%) rated the cleanliness as 3 out of 5, suggesting that there is some room for improvement. Overall, the data indicates that the majority of respondents have a positive perception of the cleanliness of 7/11 stores, but there is still some room for improvement.
- Please rate the convenience of 7/11 stores in terms of location and operating hours*
Based on the ratings, the majority of respondents (60%) rated the convenience of 7/11 stores as 5 out of 5 followed by 4 out of 5 (36%), indicating that they consider it

highly convenient in terms of location and operating hours. Overall, the data indicates that respondents perceive 7/11 stores to be highly convenient in terms of both location and operating hours.

- How would you rate the Store layout of 7/11 convenience stores? (i.e., Products are easy to find and strategically displayed)*
Majority of the respondents (60%) rated the store layout of 7/11 convenience stores as "4", indicating a positive perception of the store layout and that products are easy to find and strategically displayed. Meanwhile, 18% of respondents rated it as "3", and a smaller percentage rated it as "2" (6%) or "5" (16%). Overall, the data implies that a majority of respondents have a favorable opinion of the store layout at 7/11 convenience stores.

Table 4 Effectiveness of strategies employed by 7-Eleven Inc. in terms of *Promotion* in their Marketing Mix in dealing with challenges as perceived by customers

	1 (Not at all Effective)	2 (Not Very Effective)	3 (Neutral)	4 (Somewhat Effective)	5 (Very Effective)
Effectiveness of marketing and advertising strategies	2%	8%	34%	52%	4%
Influence of Promotion in buying behavior of customers	2%	8%	34%	50%	6%
Promotional activities or marketing campaigns	0%	8%	38%	48%	6%
Overall brand image	0%	0%	14%	72%	14%

- How do you perceive the effectiveness of the marketing and advertising strategies used by 7/11 convenience stores? (e.g., promotions, loyalty programs, social media, etc.)*
Majority of respondents (52%) rated the marketing and advertising strategies used by 7/11 convenience stores as "4", indicating a positive perception of their effectiveness. Additionally, 34% of respondents rated it as "3", and a smaller percentage rated it as "2" (8%) or "5" (4%). Only a very small percentage of respondents (2%) rated it as "1", indicating poor effectiveness. Overall, the data suggests that the majority of respondents perceive the marketing and

advertising strategies used by 7/11 convenience stores as effective or good.

- Please rate the influence of 7/11's promotions and advertisement on your buying behavior.*
Majority of respondents (50%) rated the influence of 7/11's promotions and advertisements on their buying behavior as "4", indicating a significant influence on their purchasing decisions. Additionally, a significant portion of respondents (34%) rated the influence as "3", suggesting a moderate level of influence. Meanwhile, a smaller percentage of respondents rated the influence as "1" (2%),

"2" (8%), or "5" (6%), indicating low to minimal or very high influence, respectively. Overall, the data suggests that 7/11's promotions and advertisements have a notable impact on the buying behavior of the respondents, with a significant proportion indicating a significant or moderate level of influence.

• *How would you rate the promotional activities or marketing campaigns run by 7/11 stores in attracting customers?*

Majority of respondents (48%) rated the promotional activities or marketing campaigns run by 7/11 stores as "4", indicating significant effectiveness in attracting customers. Additionally, a substantial portion of respondents (38%) rated the effectiveness as "3", suggesting a moderate level of effectiveness. Meanwhile, a smaller percentage of respondents rated the effectiveness as "1" (0%), "2" (8%), or "5" (6%), indicating low to minimal or very high

effectiveness, respectively. Overall, the data suggests that 7/11's promotional activities or marketing campaigns are perceived as effective in attracting customers by a significant proportion of the respondents, with a notable proportion indicating significant or moderate effectiveness.

• *How would you rate the overall brand image of 7/11?*

The data gathered suggests that the majority of respondents (72%) rated the overall brand image of 7/11 as "4", indicating a strong brand image. Additionally, a notable portion of respondents (14%) rated the brand image as "3", suggesting a moderate level of brand image. Meanwhile, a smaller percentage of respondents rated the brand image as "1" (0%), "2" (0%), or "5" (14%), indicating very poor, poor, or very strong brand image, respectively.

➤ *Supply chain management*

Fig 6 Effectiveness of 7-Eleven's supply chain management strategies in ensuring timely and efficient product delivery

Based on the table above, 68% of the respondents voted that the supply chain management strategies of 7-Eleven are effective in ensuring timely and efficient product delivery, while only 6% said that it is very effective. On the other hand, 26% voted neutral on this aspect.

To ease the inventory of hundreds of products in the store, 7-eleven has its own replenishment system. According to an article of Supply Chain World, 7 Eleven, the convenience store introduced a guided replenishment system, where it generates an anticipated forecast demand based on weighted sales from the previous forecast period. It is designed to quickly fulfill orders for items in low-velocity categories, reduce out-of-stock situations and grant employees more time to manage the quality of inventory.

Fig 7 Respondents' perception on the quality of products available at 7-Eleven stores in terms of freshness and shelf-life, as a result of their supply chain management practices

As a result of effective supply chain management of 7-Eleven convenience stores, 60% of the respondents said that they are satisfied with the quality of products in terms of freshness and shelf-life. According to Dean Burkett, Director of Demand Planning and Replenishment, "7-eleven is vested in the quality of products. We make sure that at the store level we have the freshest items out in the marketplace." 18% selected neutral while the remaining minority selected very satisfied (10%) and dissatisfied (12%).

Fig 8 Respondent’s level of satisfaction with the availability and variety of products at 7-Eleven convenience stores, considering their supply chain management practices

Majority (58%) of the respondents are satisfied with 7-Eleven’s availability and variety of products they offer. While 30% voted neutral, 8% very satisfied and the remaining 4% dissatisfied. Variety of products from well-known food and beverage manufacturers, body essentials and more. 7-eleven convenience store also offers on the go hot meals such as crunch time (chicken and rice), big time meals (beef gyudon and chicken teriyaki), 7-eleven all day breakfast meals, and fresh sandwiches which is a one of the game changers of the store.

Fig 9 Respondents’ perception on 7-Eleven’s responsiveness in managing supply chain disruptions or product shortages, such as during times of high demand or unforeseen events

Based on the figure above, 52% said that they are satisfied with the responsiveness of the convenient store whenever there are product shortages, especially in times of high demand or unforeseen events. On the other hand, respondents selected neutral, very satisfied, dissatisfied and very dissatisfied having 34%, 6% and 4% of responses respectively. Though shortage, especially during times of high demands and unforeseen events, is inevitable, 7-Eleven continuously strives to provide and replenish their shelves to accommodate customer demands.

➤ *Customer Service Initiatives*

Fig 10 Respondents’ rating on the professionalism and attitude of employees in providing customer service

Majority or 64% of the respondents stated that they are satisfied with the customer service of 7-Eleven’s employees in terms of professionalism and attitude. With 16% response rate, respondents selected neutral and very satisfied, only 4% said that they are dissatisfied with the employee's professionalism and attitude in providing customer service.

Fig 11 Respondent’s rating on the customer service initiatives provided by 7-Eleven employees during their complaints

More than half (54%) of respondents, who made up the majority, specified that they are satisfied with employee initiatives whenever there are complaints. On the other hand, 36% stated neutral, while a minority of 8% of the respondents said that they are very satisfied with this aspect.

D. Changes/ Improvements made by 7/11 convenience stores in response to challenges

As shown in the table below, most of the respondents stated that the recent changes they have encountered in 7-Eleven convenience stores was having an ATM machine. Installing ATMs in more stores is one of the key pillars of our Convenience Plus strategy. Convenience Plus has been our approach to meeting more customer needs since the start of this pandemic as per the company’s official. While a minority of respondents shared that there are additional 7-Eleven convenience stores in their area, updating of shelf tag, additional products such as gulp milk tea, additional services like payment center for bills and expansion of physical stores.

Table 5 Recent changes/improvements made by 7-Eleven stores observed by the respondents

Changes/Improvements Observed	Number of Respondents
Availability of ATM Machines	15
Added another 2 branches	1
Updating of shelf tag	1
Additional products	1
Payment center for bills	1
Expansion of Physical store	1
Pricing	1

Fig 12 Level of improvement made by 7-Eleven convenience stores in the past year, as per respondents’ observations.

Based on the graph shown above, 58% of the respondents said that there have been some improvements in 7-Eleven convenience stores in the past years. On the other hand, 22% stated that it has significant improvement, 14% selected no change, while the remaining 6% declined.

Fig 13 Respondents’ perception on the effective adoption of 7-Eleven convenience stores to changing customer needs and preferences

Half (50%) of the respondents agreed that the 7-Eleven convenience store has effectively adapted to changing customer needs and preferences. Whereas, 32% selected neutral, 16% strongly agree, furthermore the remaining respondents disagree.

➤ List down any changes you've noticed in the marketing and advertising strategies of 7-Eleven convenience stores in the past year. (Please type N/A if none.)

Table 6 Changes/ improvements made by 7-Eleven in their marketing and advertising strategies in the past year

Changes in marketing and advertising strategies of 7/11 convenience store in the past year	Number of Respondents
Discounts, Promotions (e.g during holidays and anniversary sales)	5
Strategically arranging on sale products	1
Trends and culture adaptive	1
Limited social media marketing	1
Signages are not attractive	1

Most of the respondents notice that posting of promotions (during holidays and anniversary sales) and discounts ahead of time are some of the marketing and advertising strategies of 7-Eleven in the past year. Respondents also noticed that the store strategically arranged products on sale near the counter/ cashier area that tempts individuals to buy because of its discounted price. The convenient store adaptability to current trends and culture was also mentioned. On the other hand, some of the respondents give emphasis on 7-Eleven’s signages that are not attractive and for having limited social media marketing.

Fig 14 Comparison of 7-Eleven's strategies with its competitors

Majority of the respondents (46%) said that 7-Eleven strategies are somewhat better than their competitors. Moreover, the remaining 34% selected the option about the same, 18% much better, and the remaining stated that it is somewhat worse.

Fig 15 Strategies to Improve/Implement at 7-Eleven

Based on the graph shown above, providing more nutritional information about products and increasing sustainability initiatives both gain 46% of the respondents’ choice. 42% stated that improving the quality of fresh food offerings are the areas 7-Eleven needs to improve and implement. Enhancing the loyalty program and reducing wait times for in-store services gain 28% and 18% of the respondents’ choice respectively. In addition, the respondents also stated their insight for the areas that needs to improve or implement such as updating of the price tags that leads to misinformation to the customers, issuance of e-receipt to reduce paper usage and cleanliness.

➤ In your opinion, which of the following strategies should 7-Eleven focus on in the future? (Select all that apply)

Fig 16 Preferred Strategies for 7-Eleven's Future Focus

Gaining 68% of the respondents’ choice, offering healthier food options should be a 7-Eleven focus on the future. According to the report of Food Industry Asia, the health consciousness of Filipino consumers is increasing. Most consumers have shown some interest in adopting healthier eating habits, eating more fruits and vegetables and reducing the intake of salt, sugar, and fat have been identified as key areas to improve in their diets. Seconded by 56% of the respondents’ choice stated that implementing new technology (e.g. mobile app, self-checkout), followed by expanding product lines with 52% votes should also be

the focus of the convenient store. While partnering with other companies were selected by 34% of the respondents. Furthermore, green marketing and cleanliness and hygiene are also mentioned by the respondents that need to give attention to the future.

IV. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The researchers conclude that the success of the 7-Eleven convenience store chain can be attributed to its marketing mix, supply chain management and customer service strategies. The respondents confirmed their satisfaction with the recent store's changes and improvements, such as the addition of ATMs and expansion of their physical locations, which have positively impacted their customers' satisfaction. The study recommends that 7-Eleven maintain these corporate strategies to preserve and strengthen its market position.

In addition, the study suggests that 7-Eleven should look into new ideas and innovations, such as implementing or incorporating blockchain technology to enhance their supply chain management – allowing them to track and trace their items more efficiently. This might also result in increased consumer loyalty and trust.

Overall, this study provides insights into the supply chain management and customer service strategies of 7-Eleven and their impact on the company's success. It also highlights potential areas for future improvements and developments for the company to maintain its market position and continue to meet the needs and expectations of its customers.

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